

QUIZ**LAST NAME: AMOS****FIRST NAME: GEORGE****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (footnotes)
The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references
The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **The following are typically found in the methodology chapter of a dissertation:**
 - Research sample; research design; method of collecting data; ethical considerations; and limitation of the study.¹**
 - Research sample; recommendations for future research; limitation of the study; and the findings of the study.
 - Research sample; research design; recommendations for action; and the findings of the study.
 - Limitation of the study; ethical considerations; the findings of the study; recommendations for future research; and research questions.

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 78-87.

2. **What three elements are at the core of an argument?**

- Evidence; source of the evidence; and compelling reasons.
- The author's education qualification; claim; and the source of the evidence.
- Claim; reasons for accepting the claim; and evidence supporting reasons.**²
- Evidence supporting the reasons; the source of the evidence; and the author's education qualification.

3. **How are sources measured or evaluated?**

- Whether the sources are relevant and reliable.**³
- Whether the sources are from an acclaimed university.
- Whether the sources are of current publications.
- Whether the sources are relevant and are of a reputable publisher.

4. **What are the aims of an introduction of a research paper?**

- An introduction should stimulate the reader to read the paper; stipulate how many pages is the paper; make readers understand why they should read the report.
- An introduction should put a research in the context of other research; make readers understand why they should read the report; give readers a framework for understanding.**⁴

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 8th ed. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 52.

³ Turabian, 33.

⁴ Ibid., 104.

- An introduction should encourage readers to begin a research in a similar field of study; put a research in the context of other research.
 - An introduction should aim to show the relevance of the study; give readers a framework for understanding the research; and stimulate the reader to read the paper.
5. **A major distinction between the US and UK English in the use of quotation marks is that:**
- In the US standard, the quote including comma and the period or other punctuations must be within the quotation marks.⁵**
 - In the UK English, only periods are included within the quotation marks.
 - In the UK English, double quotation marks are used.
 - In the US English, single quotation marks are used.
6. **A Bibliography must contain:**
- Every source cited in a note and sometimes other works consulted during the research.⁶**
 - Only those sources cited in a note.
 - Only those works cited in the literature review.
 - Few relevant sources cited in a note and every other works consulted during the research.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D: Period 1* 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 35.

⁶ Turabian, 145.

7. **Enter the following Book in a Bibliography: New York 2020, End of the Pandemic at page 115, Isuloma Anderson, Toronto Press.**

Anderson, Isuloma. *End of the Pandemic*. New York: Toronto Press, 2020.⁷

Isuloma, Anderson. 2020. End of the Pandemic, 115. New York: Toronto Press.

Anderson, Isuloma, End of the Pandemic. 2020. New York: Toronto Press, 115.

Anderson, Isuloma. *End of the Pandemic*, 115. New York: Toronto Press, 2020.

8. **The Turabian Style of citation requires that a quotation within a quotation goes**

Without quotation marks but should be placed within commas.

With double quotation marks.

With single quotation marks.⁸

With single quotation marks and italicized.

9. **With respect to participants, what four areas of information are typically needed in a qualitative study?**

Contextual, perceptual, demographical, and theoretical.⁹

Educational, gender, incremental, and perceptual.

Educational, contextual, demographical, and perceptual.

⁷ Turabian, 146.

⁸ Ibid., 349.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 69.

Theoretical, contextual, incremental, and demographical.

10. **In what ways can the trustworthiness of data collected in a qualitative research be evaluated?**

Credibility, transferability, conformability, and confirmability.

Relevancy, conformability, credibility, and applicability.

Applicability, transferability, dependability, and credibility.

Credibility, transferability, dependability, confirmability.¹⁰

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008.

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¹⁰ Ibid.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.